

THE ROLE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

¹Kadirova Khalima Buvabaevna, ²Turgunova Ozoda

¹Associate professor, TSPU named after Nizami

²1st-year student of the Faculty of Special Pedagogy of Tashkent State Pedagogical University
named after Nizami

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Abstract. *In the article the information about malicious information, destructive ideas, and threats to national morals spread through the Internet today, the demands and needs of the media for the development of the young generation growing up in the era of globalization, on the basis of national values, protection of our youth from foreign influences that undermine youth education, educating them as morally strong individuals who can resist information threats, prevention of information attacks is presented. In addition, issues such as the role of high-quality education and modern computer technology in the development of New Uzbekistan, the formation of information and media culture in the rational use of the Internet by young people have been analyzed.*

Keywords: *information, globalization, threats, media literacy, digital society, communication, internet, cyber security, national value, youth education, reading culture, legal immunity.*

In today's modern conditions, the demand for media is increasing. Because of this, the need for media literacy and information culture is increasingly felt due to the acceleration of information technology in the information society and the sharp increase in the volume of information. Therefore, the legal education of young people in terms of media literacy and the formation of their legal culture is a complex and continuous process [4, p. 6480-6487]

In the 21st century, it has become difficult to imagine our daily life and work without information media. The influence of the media on various spheres of life is increasing day by day. This puts new tasks before the educational system, requiring a person not only to know modern technical tools and the ability to work with them, but also includes independent creative work skills related critical thinking (ability to interpret media messages, understand various media texts), search, process and presentation of material to a certain extent. Let's talk about the term "media" mentioned above, it is defined in the dictionary of media terms as follows: "media (lat. media - means) - means of (mass) communication - technical means of creating, recording, copying, reproducing, storing, distributing, perceiving and exchange between the subject (the author of the media text) and the object (the public audience) [5]. We can include television, computer, radio and mobile communication devices, internet etc. among these tools. Among this content, today mobile communication devices have a special place and are important in conveying messages and information. After all, we can say that our smartphones, which are considered convenient for all of us, have become one of the technical tools that manage online life today.

Media tools are also gaining special importance in professional fields. Therefore, the role of mass media in society, their popularity among the population, requires the establishment of their proper use.[6, p. 1373-1377]

The aim of this is to further increase the information culture, literacy, and level of our young people in using modern computer technology and the Internet, and raise them to a higher potential. As the President of our country noted, “To achieve success, it is important to acquire high-quality knowledge and modern computer technology. This allows us to follow the shortest path to improvement” [1]

Using modern technology, especially the Internet, we become aware of news and information in the world and around us. On this regard Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. PD-No 5349 dated February 19, 2018 "On measures to further improve the field of information technologies and communications", PB- No.6181 dated March 4, 2021 "On approval of the concept of development of civil society in 2021-2025", Resolution PR-5040 dated March 26, 2021 "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs", Resolution No. 888 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 21, 2019 "On additional measures to promote national content in the Internet world search engine", Law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan LRU-No. 764 dated April 15, 2022 "On Cyber Security" and several regulatory documents related to the field have been adopted. After all, modern digital technology, the Internet, together with strengthening solidarity and cooperation among our multi-ethnic people, widely discovering national customs, traditions, and values, serves the formation of artistic creativity and reading culture. It is known that values become motivation when they are perceived and accepted by the individual. [7, p. 124-125]

By adapting to the informational digital society, people are acquiring the skills to use online libraries, scientific and disciplinary resources, global information resources and databases. It is in the information society that almost unlimited opportunities are emerging that affect the personal life of each person, his place in the information-computer environment. Such unlimited possibilities can change the essence of a person in a negative way. The influence of information on the formation of social opinion and technological development is becoming more and more active [8, p. 469-473].

Adaptation of a person to the informational digital society is brought up based on new requirements. That’s why E.Toffler claims that “No matter how high a person's ability to adapt, no matter how brave and durable he is, he remains a biological organism, a "biotism", he as a biosystem, like other such systems, can only function within certain limits. "Flying" humans into the future without protecting them from collisions with change would be equivalent to sending Armstrong and Aldrin naked into space” [9].

One of the main features of the informed digital society consists in not only the collection of new information [10, p. 35-42] together with finding the necessary information and maintaining the stability of information exchange but also in spreading knowledge without borders. Also, taking into account that today every information has the characteristic of having no borders, it is also the reason that preserving the national identity of the young generation, whose consciousness and worldview is just being formed, becomes one of the urgent problems. Because, in many areas, the increase in the level of information and communication, the increase in the number of Internet users increases the risk of the spread of unreliable, incorrect and illegal information and threats to information security. Due to the increase in the conflicting situations related to social, national, religious, internet networks and sexual aspects, which are emerging on the basis of the process of transformation of cultures in the countries of the world, the loss of the moral image of the nation

and the individual in the process of culturalization is becoming more and more intense [11, p. 59-60].

In our republic in recent years a legal basis on conducting preventive work against religious extremism and terrorism, drug addiction, cyber security, crime, consumption of psychotropic substances, developing legal immunity of young people, educating them in the national, perfect human spirit, and improving the spiritual and educational aspects of combating ideological threats that endanger young people is being developed. In the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "improvement of the system of combating crime and prevention of crime, strengthening organizational and operational measures to combat religious extremism and terrorism" [3] is defined as a priority task. The information and communication environment is increasingly covering all aspects of human life. After all, the fact that the Internet is becoming an ideological weapon for some people is the most problematic aspect of the issue. [12, p. 415-419].

It can be seen from this that in order to subjugate a people or a nation, it is enough to conquer the minds of the youth of that country. The "Arab Spring" crises or unrest in some regions of Europe can be cited as proof of this [13, p. 56].

Legal education and upbringing are interrelated [14, p. 5477-5489]. Today, in order to prevent information attacks, it is necessary to improve the legal immunity of young people, to further expand the possibility of media literacy and information culture. Forming the right and vigilant attitude in young people against external threats and destructive influences, improving knowledge, skills, and competence in analyzing the essence of events, educating young people based on national values, strengthening the feeling of loyalty to their people, the Motherland in their hearts, protecting them from the information of various destructive forces, warning against attacks, increasing attention to high spirituality and moral education in the era of globalization are among of the urgent tasks of youth education. Today, rapidly developing modern technologies have positive and negative effects on society.

As the first President of the Republic of Islam Islam Karimov emphasized in his work "Supreme Spirituality - Invincible Power", "If violent and aggressive forces in the world want to subjugate any nation or country and seize its wealth, they first try to disarm it, to separate from its greatest wealth, that is, from its national values, history and spirituality. Therefore, any threat to spirituality can become one of the serious threats to the security of the country, its national interests, the future of a healthy generation, and ultimately lead to a crisis in society.

Therefore, educating citizens, first of all, young people in new modern technologies and forming the experience of using them, at the same time, ensuring their broad participation in the creation and improvement of such technologies remain one of the main tasks of the basic education system. [15, p. 597-605]

This, in turn, makes it an urgent task for young people to acquire deeper knowledge, fully assimilate large-scale information and use it effectively.

: "Today's rapidly changing world opens up new and great opportunities for humanity and young people. At the same time, they are exposed to various evil dangers that have never been seen before. Malicious forces are turning simple, gullible children against their parents, their country, and are taking their lives" [2]

Today, the number of people who become victims through the Internet is increasing year by year. One of the main reasons for this is that out of curiosity or need, they fall into the evil web of wicked people. Especially in the internet networks, the evil people who disguise religion in the

way of their original goals and cause many people to go astray have also found a place for themselves in the internet networks. Even if the law against religious sects, extremism, threats and measures to prevent it are taken, it is still not possible to completely eliminate this threat. In order to prevent these unfortunate events from happening among the population, especially among the youth, it is necessary to give the child media education skills from school time.

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